

All cellulose composites reinforced with crystal nanocellulose and micro-cellulose fibers

Jing Cao, Man Jiang, * Wei Xie, David Hui and Zuowan Zhou*

Key Laboratory of Advanced Technologies of Materials (Ministry of Education), School of Materials Science and Engineering, Southwest Jiaotong University, 610031, Chengdu, P.R. China.

* jiangman1021@home.swjtu.edu.cn, zwzhou@home.swjtu.edu.cn

The potential of nanocomposites is promising in various fields of fundamental research and applications, which attracts increasing investment. In this work, we developed all cellulose composites (ACCs) reinforced by both crystal nanocellulose particles (CNC) and microcellulose fibers with diameter in nano scales (MFC). The results show that both the CNC and MFC improved the mechanical property of ACC obviously, and the MFC exhibited better enforcement as to the present results.

The crashed cotton pulp, containing 96.15% α -cellulose, 7.30% humidity, 0.62% hemicelluloses, and 0.13% ash, was completely dissolved in 55% tetrabutylammonium hydroxide (TBAH) aqueous solution in 7 wt% concentration as matrix. The CNC in length ranging from 20 to 100 nm was prepared through hydrolysis of the cotton pulp in 60% H_2SO_4 aqueous solution according to the literature.^[1] The crashed cotton pulp was dispersed in deionized water and treated with ultrasonic under 600 W for 30 MFC to obtain the MFC with 30-60 nm in diameter and aspect ratio over 50. The ACCs were prepared by introducing certain percentage of MFC or CNC to well dispersed cellulose solution under magnetic rotation, and then regenerated by deionized water after completely gelation. The tensile stress of the ACCs was increased to 172.2 MPa and 159.3 MPa from 135.8 MPa

with 20 wt% MFC and CNC as reinforcement respectively, as shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1 The stress-strain curves of the as prepared ACCs with different ratio of MFC (a) or CNC (b) as reinforcement

The morphology analysis of the tensile fracture surfaces of the regenerated matrix film and the ACCs, as shown in Fig. 2, manifested that the MFC and CNC have good interaction with the matrix, while the dispersion and the alignment are needed to be improved in the future work to obtain high performance ACC.

Fig. 2 The transparent ACC film (a) and the SEM imagines of tensile fracture surfaces of the regenerated matrix cellulose (b) and the ACCs enhanced with 20 wt% MFC (c) and CNC (d) respectively

As is known to all that the crystal structure of regenerated cellulose varies with the regeneration conditions. The prepared ACCs were analyzed by X-ray diffraction compared with the regenerated cellulose matrix and neat MFC and CNC in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3 The X-ray diffraction profiles of ACCs reinforced with different percentage of MFC (a) and CNC (b)

Cellulose III was observed according to the X-ray diffraction patterns, which manifested that the CNC and MFC have induced the crystallization process of the matrix cellulose to form cellulose III. Without the MFC and CNC the cellulose solution will regenerated into cellulose II.

Fig.4 The stress-strain curves of the ACCs cooperatively enhanced with MFC and CNC compared with separately enhanced with MFC or CNC

Furthermore, the cooperatively reinforcement of the ACC with both MFC and CNC were inspected intension to obtain synergistic effect,

and the stress-strain curves were included in Fig. 4. Although the synergistic reinforcement has not been obtained yet. That is inferred to be eliminated by the poor dispersion and alignment of the reinforcement phase and the pre-dispersion of the MFC and CNC will also have effect on the performance of the ACC.

Acknowledgement

This work was financially supported by the National Natural Science Foundation of China (No. 51303151), Sichuan Province Youth Science and Technology Innovation Team (No. 2016TD0026), Science & Technology Pillar Program of Sichuan Province (No. 2016GZ0222).

References

- 1) Ma, H., Zhou, B., Li, H., Li, Y., & Ou, S. Green composite films composed of nanocrystalline cellulose and a cellulose matrix regenerated from functionalized ionic liquid solution. *Carbohydrate Polymers*, 2011, 84: 383–389.
- 2) Abe, K., & Yano, H. Comparison of the characteristics of cellulose microfibril aggregates isolated from fiber and parenchyma cells of Moso bamboo (*Phyllostachys pubescens*). *Cellulose*, 2010, 17(2): 271–277.
- 3) Abe, K., & Yano, H. Comparison of the characteristics of cellulose microfibril aggregates of wood, rice straw and potato tuber. *Cellulose*, 2009, 16(6): 1017–1023.